

Z-Expansion Revisited

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Two different Padé approximants simulating the ground state energies of neutral atoms are obtained. An average density argument has been applied to obtain the Z-dependence of various momentum expectation values. The results in the former calculation are quite good. The latter calculation produces acceptable results when one considers the computational simplicity.

To obtain the total binding energy of neutral atoms with only atomic number (Z) as the input has been considered to be an important problem by many workers¹. Of late, there has been a great upsurge of interest in this age-old problem after Lieb and Simon² proved that the Thomas-Fermi (TF) theory³ produces exact binding energy for atoms having Z going to infinity. In the limit of Z tending towards infinity the ground state energy can be written, within the Thomas-Fermi-Scott-Schwinger (TFSS) framework, as

$$-E_{\text{TFSS}}(Z) = C_7 Z^{7/3} + C_6 Z^2 + C_5 Z^{5/3} \quad (1)$$

where $C_7 = 0.76874512$ (TF value³), $C_6 = -0.5$ (Scott value⁴) and $C_5 = 0.2699$ (Schwinger value⁵). Although equation (1) produces the energy within 8%⁵ the term beyond $Z^{5/3}$ have been considered to be oscillatory in nature and are discontinuous functions of Z^{6-8} . It has also been felt⁷ that extending the TFSS expansion (1) will be a challenging endeavour. Chattaraj *et al.*¹ extended equation (1) to include two more terms obtained from well-known physical effects. The modified-TFSS (MTFSS) energy expression¹ is given by

$$-E_{\text{MTFSS}}(Z) = -E_{\text{TFSS}}(Z) + C_4 Z^{4/3} + C_3 Z \quad (2)$$

where $C_4 = 0.0129783$ and $C_3 = 0.00126492$. It is important to note that the two terms beyond $Z^{5/3}$ are neither oscillatory nor discontinuous. From the physics behind the derivation of different terms¹ it is clear that equation (2) contains terms upto

exchange energy and hence approximates the Hartree-Fock level energies. The oscillation, if there is any, should be there in the correlation term. Chattaraj *et al.*¹ argued that the correlation terms cannot be expressed as a simple algebraic function of $Z^{1/3}$. They have obtained the energy expression which simulates the nonrelativistic energy as

$$-E_{\text{MTFSS}}(Z) = -E_{\text{TFSS}}(Z) + \frac{Z}{[9.810 + 21.437(Z^2/V_0)^{-1/3}]} \quad (2a)$$

where V_0 is a universal constant.

Aguilera-Navarro *et al.*⁷ obtained the Padé approximant whose coefficients are obtained by matching the Z expansion of the approximant to equation (1) and the small Z expansion of it to the exact Bohr formula for hydrogen atom, viz.

$$-F(Z) = 0.5 Z^2 \quad (Z = 1) \quad (3)$$

It must be pointed out that the energy for hydrogen atom cannot be calculated from their approximant because their expansion variable is $(Z-1)^{-1/3}$ and equation (3) is applicable only for hydrogen atom. This is probably one of the reasons for their low Z energy values not being very good. These authors have also seen huge well-defined oscillations for all Z . In order to improve the energy values, particularly for low Z , as well as to understand

the nature of oscillations better, we have constructed two different Padé approximants whose coefficients are determined by making use of equations (2) and (3) in connection with exact nonrelativistic energy values for three closed shell atoms. The numerical details are described in the first section.

Different moments of momentum are also important physical observables like ground state energy. For example, $\langle p^k \rangle$ with $k = -1, 0, 1, 2, 4$ are related to the peak value of the compton profile, the normalisation constant, the free-electron model atomic exchange energy, the kinetic energy and the relativistic corrections respectively.

Within the TF framework the momentum expectation values can be expressed as single-particle density functionals,

$$\langle p^k \rangle = \frac{3}{3+k} (3\pi^2)^{k/3} \langle \rho \frac{k+3}{3}(\vec{r}) \rangle \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(\vec{r})$ is the electron density at \vec{r} ;

The Z-dependence for the k -th moment of momentum can easily be obtained in case one resorts to the average density technique¹. The second section deals with the corresponding calculation procedure while the results and discussion are presented in the third section.

Padé approximants for ground state energies of neutral atoms :

Here we consider two different Padé approximants, viz.

$P_{3,3}(x)$ and $P_{4,4}(x)$ where $x = Z^{1/3}$. We write equation (2) as

$$\begin{aligned} -E_{\text{MTFSS}}(Z) &= \frac{C_7 Z^{7/3} + C_6 Z^2 + C_5 Z^{5/3} + C_4 Z^{4/3} + C_3 Z}{C_4 Z^{4/3} + C_3 Z} \\ &= T_0(Z) + T_2(Z) + C_5 Z^{5/3} + C_4 Z^{4/3} + C_3 Z \\ &= T_0(Z) P_{n,m} \left(\frac{T_0(Z)}{T_2(Z)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $T_0(Z)$ is Thomas-Fermi term and $T_2(Z)$

is the Scott term which is related to Weizsäcker functional¹. For dimensional homogeneity only diagonal Padé approximants are considered.

For the $P_{3,3}(x)$ the approximate energy is written as

$$-E_{3,3}(x) = C_7 x^7 \frac{\sum_{i=0}^3 a_i x^i}{\sum_{i=0}^3 b_i x^i} \quad (6)$$

where $x = Z^{7/3}/Z^2 = Z^{1/3}$ and a_0 has been taken as unity. Other coefficients are obtained by equating coefficients of like powers of x in both the sides of equation (6) and taking $E_{3,3}(x) = E_{\text{MTFSS}}(x)$. Remaining three unknowns are obtained by solving three simultaneous equations obtainable from the exact nonrelativistic ground state energy values⁹ for three closed shell atoms, viz. He, Ne and Ar.

In order to obtain the coefficients of $P_{4,4}(x)$ we take b_4 (here r_4) to be unity and also demand that equation (5) should satisfy the Bohr formula (3) for hydrogen atom. The energy expression with $P_{4,4}(x)$ is written as

$$-E_{4,4}(x) = C_7 x^7 \frac{\sum_{k=0}^4 q_k x^k}{\sum_{k=0}^4 r_k x^k} \quad (7)$$

All the coefficients $\{a_i, b_i\}$ and $\{q_k, r_k\}$ are reported in Table 1.

Z-dependence of momentum expectation values of neutral atoms :

Momentum expectation values have been calculated within TF, TF-Weizsäcker (TFW)¹⁰, TF-Scott (TFS)¹¹ and Hartree-Fock (HF)¹² frameworks. Here, we use the average density approach to obtain the Z-dependence of different momentum

TABLE 1—THE COEFFICIENTS OF $P_{3,3}(x)$ AND $P_{4,4}(x)$ DEFINED IN EQUATIONS (6) AND (7) RESPECTIVELY

	$P_{3,3}(x)$		$P_{4,4}(x)$
a_0	1	q_0	1.162 565 1
a_1	-2.752 231 4	q_1	-3.693 859 1
a_2	3.339 992 9	q_2	6.273 557 4
a_3	-0.936 361 9	q_3	-4.621 632 3
b_0	-0.363 978 1	q_4	1
b_1	-6.472 285	r_0	-0.038 444 4
b_2	2.730 973 1	r_1	-0.144 405 8
b_3	-0.936 361 9	r_2	3.339 540 8
		r_3	-3.971 221 7
		r_4	1

expectation values within TF framework. If $f(\rho)$ is a local function of $\rho(r)$ and $F[\rho]$ its volume integral, then the Z-dependence of F is given by¹,

$$\begin{aligned}
 F &= \int f(\rho) dr \\
 &= f(\bar{\rho}) V \\
 &= f(\bar{Z}^2/V_0) V_0 Z^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where V is the TF volume¹³ of a neutral atom with Z electrons, $\bar{\rho} = Z/V$ is the average density and the volume V_0 is a universal constant having value 7.218207. Writing different moments of momentum as density functional within TF model (equation 4) and making use of equation (8) we obtain the following relations,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle p^{-2} \rangle &= 1.1707392 Z^{-1/3} \\
 \langle p^{-1} \rangle &= 0.9370455 Z^{1/3} \\
 \langle p^0 \rangle &= Z \\
 \langle p^1 \rangle &= 1.2005819 Z^{5/3} \\
 \langle p^2 \rangle &= 1.5374901 Z^{7/3} \\
 \langle p^3 \rangle &= 2.0509812 Z^3 \\
 \langle p^4 \rangle &= 2.8128146 Z^{11/3}
 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Instead of going for a gradient correction to TF functional we try to fit the above expectation values for different neutral atoms with the corresponding HF values¹² in a least-square sense to obtain the following set of modified relations,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle p^{-2} \rangle &= 95.475461 Z^{-1/3} \\
 \langle p^{-1} \rangle &= 4.6205536 Z^{1/3} \\
 \langle p^0 \rangle &= Z \\
 \langle p^1 \rangle &= 0.7098718 Z^{5/3} \\
 \langle p^2 \rangle &= 1.3017976 Z^{7/3} \\
 \langle p^3 \rangle &= 5.1443638 Z^3 \\
 \langle p^4 \rangle &= 44.619167 Z^{11/3}
 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Results and Discussion

Table 2 compares the energy values for several neutral atoms calculated using different Padé approximants with the corresponding ground state nonrelativistic (NR) values⁹ wherever available. For comparison, the energy values calculated by Chattaraj

 TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF $-E(Z)$ VALUES (a.u.) FOR NEUTRAL ATOMS WITH NONRELATIVISTIC ENERGIES WHEREVER AVAILABLE

Z	$-E_{\text{MTFSS}}^a$	$-E_{\text{AN}}^b$	$-E_{3,3}^c$	$-E_{4,4}^d$	$-E_{\text{NR}}^e$
1	0.553	-	0.639	0.500	0.5
2	2.766	2.689	2.904	2.904	2.904
3	7.223	7.139	7.410	7.351	7.478
4	14.333	14.260	14.569	14.485	14.667
5	24.427	24.380	24.710	24.613	24.653
10	128.441	128.679	128.928	128.928	128.928
15	339.198	339.896	339.652	340.484	341.240
20	675.181	676.453	676.708	681.640	676.75 ^f
40	3 534.611	3 538.842	3 536.767	3 533.04	3 538.996 ^f
80	18 404.965	18 416.646	18 409.011	18 403.8	
90	24 348.155	24 361.872	24 352.677	24 346.9	

^aRef. 9. ^bEqn. (2). ^cRef. 7. ^eEqn. (6). ^dEqn. (7). ^eRef. (9). ^fFrom Ref. 15.

*et al.*¹ are also included in Table 2. Present calculation provides excellent energy values particularly for low Z . In most of the smaller atoms the energy obtained from our formula are by far the best. Aguilera-Navarro *et al.* (AN)⁷ values are marginally better for certain larger atoms. The maximum percentage errors for $E_{3,3}(x)$, $E_{4,4}(x)$ and $E_{AN}(x)$ are respectively 0.9% (Li), 1.7% (Li) and 7.4% (He).

In order to study the nature of the oscillation we have calculated the quantity $(E_{\text{approx.}} - E_{\text{exact}})/Z^{7/3}$,

where E_{exact} is the exact NR values and $E_{\text{approx.}}$ may be any one of those Padé approximants or the MTFSSC value (equation 2a). For $Z > 18$, the exact NR values are not available where we have added -0.05 a.u. per electron¹⁴ as correlation energy to the corresponding HF value¹⁵. Fig. 1 depicts the variation of above quantity, for different $E_{\text{approx.}}$, with Z . Although there are oscillations for the present $E_{\text{approx.}}$ values (equations 6 and 7) they are not very large as in the case of AN⁷ or MTFSSC (equation 2a) energy values. Before making any definite comment regarding

TABLE 3—MOMENTUM EXPECTATION VALUES (a.u.) FOR NEUTRAL ATOMS*

Z	$\langle p^{-2} \rangle$	$\langle p^{-1} \rangle$	$\langle p^0 \rangle$	$\langle p^1 \rangle$	$\langle p^2 \rangle$	$\langle p^3 \rangle$	$\langle p^4 \rangle$
1	95.475	9.204	1	0.552	0.537	0.631	-0.151
		4.621	1	0.710	1.302	5.144	44.619
2		11.575	2	1.920	3.749	11.326	52.377
	75.779	5.822	2	2.254	6.561	41.155	566.63
	4.089	2.141	2	2.799	5.724	17.992	105.68
3		13.243	3	3.905	10.957	50.616	400.08
	66.199	6.664	3	4.430	16.898	138.90	2 505.9
	26.556	5.186	3	4.906	14.865	70.994	623.66
4		14.573	4	6.427	23.050	140.82	1 533.9
	60.146	7.335	4	7.155	33.064	329.24	7 195.7
	25.291	6.318	4	7.434	29.146	185.59	2 160.9
5		15.696	5	9.435	40.727	306.60	4 213.3
	55.834	7.901	5	10.378	55.651	643.05	1 630.8
	16.262	5.980	5	10.649	49.058	383.70	5 542.1
10		19.772	10	30.786	231.24	3 237.3	87 440
	44.316	9.955	10	32.949	280.46	5 144.4	0.207×10^6
	5.480	5.456	10	35.197	257.09	3 584.3	98 595
15		22.632	15	61.171	628.16	12 475	0.492×10^6
	38.713	11.395	15	64.764	722.36	17 362	0.916×10^6
	18.727	10.135	15	66.184	681.43	13 464	0.534×10^6
20		24.909	20	99.402	1 269.4	32 175	0.165×10^7
	35.174	12.542	20	104.61	1 413.4	41 155	0.263×10^7
	60.821	15.749	20	103.93	1 353.5	34 307	0.177×10^7
40		31.382	40	318.91	6 813.1	0.308×10^6	0.297×10^8
	27.917	15.802	40	332.11	7 123.3	0.329×10^6	0.334×10^8
	13.772	14.682	40	333.52	7 077.6	0.318×10^6	0.306×10^8
80		39.538	80	1 019.1	35 999	0.286×10^7	0.516×10^9
	22.158	19.909	80	1 054.4	35 899	0.263×10^7	0.424×10^9
		41.121	90	1 241.2	47 710	0.417×10^7	0.836×10^9
90	21.305	20.707	90	1 283.1	47 254	0.375×10^7	0.653×10^9

*In column 2, the first no. is from present calculation (eqn. 10) and the second one is the Hartree-Fock (HF) value¹². In columns 3-8, the first, second and third numbers are respectively the Thomas-Fermi-Scott value¹¹, present calculation result (eqn. 10) and the HF value¹². For $Z = 1$ and $Z > 40$, the HF values are not entered.

Fig. 1. Plots of $(E_{\text{approx}} - E_{\text{exact}})/Z^{7/3}$ vs Z for neutral atoms :
 (—•—) $E_{\text{approx}} = E_{\text{MTFSSC}}$ (equation 2a), (—•—•—) $E_{\text{approx}} = E_{\text{AN}}$ (Ref. 7), (---) $E_{\text{approx}} = E_{3,3}$ (equation 6) and (—) $E_{\text{approx}} = E_{4,4}$ (equation 7).

the oscillatory nature and associated discontinuity or non-analyticity one should fall back upon the physics of different terms in equation (2) and should confirm whether any more terms, arising out of gradient correction to kinetic energy or exchange energy, would appear in it. Then the nature of the correlation energy functional will also be better understood.

Different momentum expectation values are reported in Table 3. The results from the relations (10) are compared with their HF¹² or TFS¹¹ counterparts. Because our calculation is mainly within the TF level it is expected to give results slightly removed from the HF or TFS values especially for low Z . For $\langle p^{-2} \rangle$, the HF values oscillate while the present calculation results are monotonically decreasing as Z increases. For very few atoms the matching is good, $\langle p^{-1} \rangle$ and $\langle p^1 \rangle$ values are much better than corresponding TFS counterparts whereas the TFS values are better for $\langle p^3 \rangle$ and $\langle p^4 \rangle$ when compared with the HF results. $\langle p^0 \rangle$ values are satisfied analytically for all the calculations. $\langle p^2 \rangle$ values from the present calculation are better than the TFS values for low Z atoms.

Considering the ridiculously simple procedure for the derivation of different relations and even simpler method for the numerical calculation it is quite gratifying that these values compare very well with the corresponding HF values¹⁶. This work has potential in case applied to ions or to excited states as well as by taking different gradient corrections to the TF term.

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